

Towards sustainable wellbeing: Integrated policies and transformative indicators.

Deliverable 3.2

Policy recommendations on alternative growth initiatives

***WP3 Identifying innovative policy options and understanding
processes of change***

Final version | *March 2026*

HORIZON-CL2-2022-TRANSFORMATIONS-01 -
Towards sustainable wellbeing: Integrated policies
and transformative indicators.

toberesearch.eu

The ToBe project is funded by the European Union in the framework of the Horizon Europe Research and Innovation Programme under grant agreement N° 101094211, and by the UK Research and Innovation (UKRI) under the UK government's Horizon Europe funding guarantee N° 10052343.

Disclaimer

This project has received funding from the European Union in the framework of the Horizon Europe Research and Innovation Programme under grant agreement N° 101094211. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the Agency. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

Copyright message

ToBe is a Horizon Europe Project supported by the European Commission under contract No. 101094211. All trademarks and other rights on third-party products mentioned in this document are acknowledged and owned by the respective holders.

The information contained in this document represents the view of the authors as of the date they are published. The ToBe consortium does not guarantee that any information contained herein is error-free, or up to date, nor makes warranties, express, implied, or statutory, by publishing this document.

How to cite this publication: Rilla, N., Nieminen, M., Bhatia, R., Herselman, M., Angresius, L., Büchs, M., Cuestas Caza, J., Escobar Urbina, G. (2026). Policy recommendations on alternative growth initiatives.

Contents

1. Introduction	6
2. Summary of policy recommendations on alternative growth initiatives	8
2.1 Key learnings from the Global North and Global South	10
3. Towards post-growth in Europe: government-led initiatives	14
4. Towards post-growth food systems: examples from Europe and South Africa	19
4.1 Post-growth and agrifood in Europe	20
4.2 Green growth and agrifood in South Africa	27
4.2.1 Policy recommendations for grassroots -driven green growth	28
5. Beyond growth: post-development perspectives from Ecuador	35
5.1 Policy recommendations from a post-development and pluriversal perspective	37
5.1.1 Key policy areas in the Ecuadorian wellbeing trajectories	45
References	47
Appendix 1: European agrifood policy labs	53
Appendix 2: South African policy labs	53
Appendix 3: Territorial research and fieldwork in Ecuador	54

Document History

Deliverable Title	Policy recommendations on alternative growth initiatives
Brief Description	This deliverable examines how alternative growth approaches—green growth, post-growth, and post-development—can inform transformative policymaking toward sustainable wellbeing across Europe, South Africa, and Ecuador. Drawing on interviews, policy labs, and territorial fieldwork, the report analyses how political, economic, social, technological, environmental, and legal (PESTEL) forces shape both barriers and opportunities for systemic change. European cases highlight government-led post-growth initiatives and agrifood transitions, while South African grassroots innovations reveal community-driven green growth shaped by Ubuntu. Ecuadorian experiences demonstrate pluriversal, post-development pathways rooted in Indigenous territoriality and sufficiency, showing that “sustainable wellbeing trajectories are not structured around economic growth.” The report concludes with cross-context policy recommendations emphasising coalition-building, context-sensitive governance, territorial knowledge, and organisational models oriented toward sufficiency, resilience, and ecological care.
WP Number	WP3
Lead Beneficiary	VTT
Author(s)	Nina Rilla (VTT), Mika Nieminen (VTT), Riina Bhatia (VTT), Marlien Herselman (CSIR), Laura Angresius (UB), Milena Büchs (Leeds), Javier Cuestas Caza (EPN), Gabriel Escobar Urbina (EPN)
Contributor(s)	Alessia Greselin (TAU), Saija Iivonen (TAU), Tuuli Hirvilammi (TAU), Maria Salonen (TAU)
Deliverable Due Date	31.3.2026
Dissemination Level	Public
DOI	
KEYWORDS	<i>Policy, post-growth, sustainable wellbeing, grassroots, sumak kawsay</i>

Date	Ver	Contributors	Comment
31.12.2025	1.1	<i>Nina Rilla (VTT), Mika Nieminen (VTT), Riina Bhatia (VTT), Marlien Herselman (CSIR), Laura Angresius (UB), Milena Büchs (Leeds), Javier Cuestas Caza (EPN), Gabriel Escobar Urbina (EPN)</i>	<i>First draft of the document</i>
12.3.2026	1.2	<i>Alessia Greselin (TAU), Saija Iivonen (TAU)</i>	<i>Revision</i>

27.3.2026	1.3	<i>Tuuli Hirvilammi (TAU), Maria Salonen (TAU)</i>	<i>Revision</i>
30.3.2026	1.4	<i>Nina Rilla (VTT), Mika Nieminen (VTT), Riina Bhatia (VTT), Marlien Herselman (CSIR), Laura Angresius (UB), Milena Büchs (Leeds), Javier Cuestas Caza (EPN), Gabriel Escobar Urbina (EPN)</i>	<i>Revised document</i>

1. Introduction

Our research explored opportunities and challenges for post-growth transformations through government-led post-growth initiatives in the Global North and economic renewal through grass-roots initiatives in the Global South. Specifically, we focused on how dynamics of drivers, barriers and outcomes of alternative growth initiatives contribute to larger economic systems and practices in South Africa, Ecuador and EU policymaking. We explored both grassroots and government-led approaches to understand different agents and processes of change.

The Global South cases offer examples of grassroots, bottom-up initiatives that integrate local development aspirations with crucial livelihood and economic questions, global economic dynamics, value-chain configurations, and postcolonial considerations. To get more concrete examples of local change dynamics, we investigated food system transformation through agrifood initiatives. The original plan was to complement a more focused case research approach with European local and city-level case studies. However, despite several attempts, it became evident that the prospective municipal and city partners were unable to participate, largely due to workload constraints. Consequently, it was decided that the investigation at the European level would instead focus on the conditions for alternative policymaking, particularly in relation to post-growth initiatives. This more general view on government-led initiatives was then complemented with an additional European focus on sustainable food production, mainly in the policy workshops organised with European stakeholders. The overarching idea was that the Global South and European studies would provide complementary perspectives on the opportunities and challenges of policymaking in an ongoing sustainability transition of food systems – being a crucial building block of the wellbeing economy in the Global South and the Global North.

To explore complex and systemic change, this report adopts a multi-level and multi-criteria approach for developing policy recommendations. With a PESTEL analysis, we increase understanding of societal change processes by breaking down the forces that shape how people live, behave, and interact with institutions, technology, and each other. The PESTEL framework offers a structured way to observe how **P**olitical, **E**conomic, **S**ocial, **T**echnological, **E**nvironmental, and **L**egal forces interact to shape people's behaviours, expectations, and values to achieve change, or even transformation (e.g., Johnson et al., 2017; Yüksel, 2012). In the context of this report, it helps us to explore how economic changes are driven and halted from these viewpoints.

Furthermore, we are interested in the tensions that may emerge between different sustainable development discourses and underlying assumptions at the local grassroots level and those embedded in national or international policy frameworks. A key question concerns which local initiatives and bottom-up ideas align with broader strategic orientations, both in policymaking and in practice. This inquiry also relates to the broader challenge of multi-level governance: to what extent are policies and

initiatives across local, national, and international levels coordinated, mutually reinforcing, or, conversely, in conflict with one another?

This issue is crucial from the perspective of systemic transformation. When policies and initiatives are coherent and supportive across governance levels, the likelihood of achieving the necessary sustainability transitions increases, reducing the risk of unnecessary tensions or repeated negotiations over the direction and objectives of such transformations.

The recommendations for advancing local growth initiatives introduced in this deliverable are formulated and disseminated to local decision-makers and other stakeholders in separate context-specific policy briefs. To increase accessibility, the recommendations are formulated into policy briefs in the local languages using visuals and neutral vocabulary.

We begin the report by outlining different approaches for understanding how change can be fostered within growth-related initiatives that emerge from local or alternative contexts. We then introduce the dynamics of change across such initiatives using the PESTEL framework as an analytical lens. Section 2 concludes by summarising a set of overarching policy recommendations, illustrated with case-based examples from both the Global North and the Global South.

The subsequent sections elaborate on policy recommendations in relation to our diverse empirical contexts. Section 3 examines European government-led post-growth transformations, followed in Section 4 by a more context-specific analysis of local agrifood initiatives in Europe and South Africa. Finally, Section 5 presents an empirical discussion of post-development transformations in Ecuador.

The overall logic of the structure is to provide, first, a comprehensive overview with actionable policy recommendations—serving as both a quick reference for a busy reader and an orienting framework for others—before moving into more detailed discussions. We proceed from a European, government-centred perspective on post-growth policymaking, analysing the opportunities and dilemmas that arise within administrative settings. We then shift to local Global South cases to explore the potential of grassroots initiatives, from which European contexts may also draw lessons when considering possible pathways toward post-growth futures.

Across these contexts, a key bridging question emerges: how can multidimensional dialogue among diverse actors—from local citizens to macro-level policymakers—be supported in ways that enable shared visions and coherent future-oriented action?

2. Summary of policy recommendations on alternative growth initiatives

Our typology of alternative growth initiatives was built on green growth, post-growth and post-development approaches (e.g., Facer et al., 2014; van den Bergh and Kallis, 2012). In between **green growth** and **post-development**, we position **post-growth**, which makes a distinction between a-growth and de-growth positions. While a-growth is growth-agnostic, de-growth is a more growth-critical approach, and these represent the central division in post-growth thinking (see Büchs et al., 2023).

Each of these approaches understands societal change in its own unique way. While green growth approaches rely mostly on market mechanisms to “green” economic growth, post-growth questions the future viability of growth in the context of accelerating climate and ecological emergencies and focuses on transforming economies to achieve wellbeing for all within planetary boundaries. Post-development approaches promote sustainable wellbeing approaches for the Global South that diverge from Western growth-centred paradigms and focus on empowering bottom-up solutions to socioecological challenges.

While green growth positions assume that it is possible to combine staying within planetary boundaries with GDP growth through decoupling (Jacobs, 2016), de-growth positions question that decoupling is possible based on the lack of evidence of absolute decoupling at the global level and at the required scale and speed (e.g., Hickel & Kallis, 2020). Post-development proposes rethinking the mainstream development paradigm by proposing new social structures based on different conceptions of the economy (e.g. replacing the global market with solidarity and reciprocity), politics (replacing centralised authorities with direct democracy) and knowledge (replacing modern knowledge systems with traditional, hybrid or both) (Ziai, 2007). This is because traditional growth-oriented development concepts have led to unsustainable exploitation of natural resources and environmental degradation (Martinez-Alier, 2014).

Furthermore, to understand transformations towards sustainable well-being economies, our research has been influenced by different theories of change that have been further elaborated in Büchs et al. (2023). For example, transition studies (e.g., the multi-level perspective), long wave theories, and transformative innovation policy approach help understand green growth change, whereas radical sustainability transformations, leverage points in systems theory, and political economy theories offer analytical tools for post-growth change. Rights of nature approaches help, in turn, understanding possible drivers and barriers to the adoption of sustainable wellbeing initiatives related to post-development perspectives.

To synthesise the findings from our research in sections 3, 4 and 5, we use a PESTEL framework that illustrates different types of forces contributing to change. Table 1 exhibits political, economic, social,

technological, environmental and legal forces accelerating change within green growth, post-growth and post-development that were selected as alternative economic approaches in the study. The change dynamics presented in Table 1 combine insights from existing literature summarising the basic ideas of different development views, their differences and potential tensions, and provide a background for the forthcoming discussion.

Table 1. Change dynamics in different growth initiatives

PESTEL			
Change dynamics in different growth initiatives			
	Green growth	Post-growth	Post-development
Political	Top-down, correcting market failures. E.g. R&D investments in ‘clean’ sectors	Top-down & bottom-up; adoption of beyond GDP indicators, regulation, reduction of matter-energy throughput, prioritisation of social and ecological well-being over GDP growth	Decentralised, bottom-up decolonial perspective, embracing epistemic pluralism; revalorization of vernacular cultures and on the practices of social movements
Economic	Utilising market mechanisms (carbon trading and internalising externalities into prices), moving from brown growth to green growth	Disregarding economic growth as a policy objective, instead focusing on social and ecological priorities	Replacing the global market with a system based on solidarity and reciprocity, and commons-based production
Social (cultural)	Material understanding of wellbeing; Economic growth increases human well-being	Sustainable well-being; Prioritisation of social welfare, localisation, sufficiency and commons	Grassroots movements driven by indigenous worldviews and local knowledge, such as urban and rural communities and the informal sector
Technological	Technological advances increase energy and material efficiency and productivity. Technological development is at the heart of sustainability transformations	Technological development is needed but not enough, due to the rebound effect. Low and convivial technology is needed to reduce matter-energy throughput and enhance the user’s autonomy	Pluriversal technologies; embracing ontological and epistemological diversity by involving individuals from diverse socio-cultural backgrounds in the collaborative design, production, and ownership of technologies
Ecological / environmental	Internalisation of externalities, carbon tax, and decoupling	Planetary boundaries - approach, quotas, protection	Environment is part of the community, relationality and reciprocity – human activities fit bioregional characters
Legal	Sustainability typologies and steering mechanisms	Regulatory frameworks that break path dependencies of	Legal systems are seen as active carriers of the development paradigm.

		production, exchange, and governance.	Transformation to pluralistic legal systems.
--	--	---------------------------------------	--

2.1 Key learnings from the Global North and Global South

Across all contexts, a structural cross-cutting barrier is the embeddedness of the growth paradigm in both material infrastructure and institutional culture. Equally consistent is the finding that fragmentation — across governance levels, policy sectors, and development approaches — limits the coherence and cumulative force of transformative initiatives. The empirical cases (European post-growth governance, European and South African agrifood, and Ecuadorian post-development perspective) complement rather than contradict one another: where European cases highlight reform pathways within existing institutions, and South African cases foreground grassroots-driven green growth, the Ecuadorian case demonstrates that sustainable wellbeing can be organised entirely outside the hegemonic growth paradigm, reinforcing the need for policies capable of engaging with plural, territorially embedded pathways of change.

With the help of PESTEL analysis, we have formulated four overarching policy recommendations to help key stakeholders — primarily decision-makers — promote and implement growth perspectives that offer alternatives to the prevailing ones. We draw on practical examples from the Global South and the Global North to illustrate both the plurality of views and approaches, and the similar challenges encountered in building open and mutual dialogue between stakeholders.

POLICY RECOMMENDATION 1: Recognise and respect context-specific language and strategies for local and alternative growth initiatives

Language and framing are not merely communicative choices — they shape what kinds of initiatives become legible, legitimate, and politically viable. What counts as growth, wellbeing, or sustainability is contested and context-dependent, and policy design must reflect this.

In European governance contexts, elected officials have used public platforms — including parliamentary debates — to critically engage with prevailing growth orthodoxies and hold space for alternative economic approaches in political discourse, even when they adopt more cautious positions in direct negotiations. In the EU agrifood context, the tension between the dominant productivity framing of instruments such as the CAP and the language of ecological transition in the Green Deal illustrates how competing framings coexist within the same governance space, making room for actors who can navigate and strategically deploy both.

From a South African perspective, context-specificity means distinguishing between rural and urban realities — recognising the distinct constraints of remoteness, land scarcity, and infrastructure gaps — and reframing growth beyond GDP to encompass wellbeing, food security, and climate resilience. It means embedding participatory and co-creation approaches so that grassroots voices genuinely inform policy design and monitoring and integrating informal and community-based systems — cooperatives, local markets, traditional structures — into formal frameworks as legitimate components of alternative growth.

From an Ecuadorian perspective, context-specificity goes further still, requiring that Indigenous conceptions of wellbeing — rooted in reciprocity, collective life, territorial continuity, and the reproduction of life — be recognised as valid policy entry points rather than marginal footnotes. Uniform frameworks fail in the face of genuine territorial diversity; differentiated approaches that reflect the distinct conditions of Indigenous and rural communities are not a concession to complexity but a condition for policy relevance and legitimacy.

POLICY RECOMMENDATION 2: Develop encouraging narratives and create significance for local and alternative growth initiatives

Transformative initiatives need not only resources and regulatory space but also cultural legitimacy and narrative traction. How alternative approaches are publicly framed determines whether they attract support, inspire imitation, or remain isolated experiments.

In European governance contexts, concepts such as the wellbeing economy or the good life have proven useful in questioning growth-oriented policy priorities and making tangible what is to be gained from a post-growth reorientation — shifting the conversation from sacrifice and restriction toward flourishing and possibility. In the EU agrifood context, short supply chains, community-supported agriculture, and agroecological practices have begun to be framed not as niche or romantic alternatives but as contributors to food system resilience, rural vitality, and ecological regeneration, connecting local initiatives to broader European priorities.

From a South African perspective, effective narratives shift from deficit to asset-based framing, positioning small-scale farmers and communities as drivers of innovation and resilience rather than as beneficiaries of aid. Linking grassroots initiatives to nationally recognised priorities — food security, job creation, youth employment, women's empowerment — creates forward-looking momentum and broadens the coalition of those who recognise a stake in their success. Real success stories, community narratives, and demonstration projects are essential here: they build credibility and public trust in ways that abstract policy arguments rarely can.

From an Ecuadorian perspective, the key move is to make visible the territorial innovations that are already underway — responses to socio-environmental challenges emerging from Indigenous

communities and local networks that often remain marginal within formal policy frameworks. These initiatives gain significance when framed not only as environmental or productive responses but as practices tied to identity, territorial defence, and community life. Crucially, ecological care and material livelihood needs must be presented together; narratives that acknowledge the real tension between sustainability goals and the need for income and dignified living conditions are more honest and ultimately more persuasive than those that paper over it.

POLICY RECOMMENDATION 3: Build coalitions for promoting local and alternative growth initiatives

No single actor can drive the transition toward sustainable wellbeing alone. Coalitions that bring together public officials, civil society organisations, researchers, communities, and market actors are essential both for advancing alternative initiatives and for giving them the political durability they need to survive beyond individual mandates or projects.

In European governance contexts, public officials committed to post-growth positions have built networks with like-minded colleagues within government while simultaneously cultivating connections with civil society organisations and academics, introducing critical perspectives into policymaking procedures that might otherwise remain closed to them. In the EU agrifood context, multi-actor platforms — bringing together farmers, processors, retailers, researchers, and policymakers — have demonstrated the potential to shift the terms of debate around supply chain governance, fair pricing, and the redistribution of value along food chains.

From a South African perspective, effective coalition-building requires a multi-actor ecosystem approach in which government, communities, research institutions, financiers, private sector actors, and intermediaries act in a coordinated rather than fragmented way. Cross-sphere alignment — integrating national, provincial, and municipal frameworks — is essential to ensure coherence across sectors and territories. Small-scale farmers and communities must be positioned as equal partners rather than passive recipients, with co-creation, trust, and shared decision-making as the foundation. Intermediary organisations — innovation hubs, extension services, research councils, and multi-stakeholder platforms — play a crucial connecting role, translating between policy logics, market realities, and community needs.

From an Ecuadorian perspective, effective coalitions require broadening participation beyond the usual interlocutors and structuring engagement according to differentiated roles — technical support, finance, regulation, commercialisation, territorial governance, knowledge exchange — rather than treating all stakeholders as interchangeable. Crucially, coalitions must be sustained through reciprocity, agreed follow-up, and forms of practical accompaniment that communities recognise as genuinely useful rather than extractive.

POLICY RECOMMENDATION 4: Support alternative organisational and business models oriented toward sufficiency and territorial embeddedness

Transformative change in economic systems requires not only new policies and narratives but also new organisational forms — ways of structuring production, exchange, and governance that do not reproduce the growth imperatives and profit maximisation logics of conventional firm models.

In European governance contexts, post-growth advocates have pointed to cooperatives, commons-based institutions, and not-for-profit enterprises as organisational alternatives capable of embedding economic activity in social and ecological relationships. In the EU agrifood context, community-supported agriculture schemes, food cooperatives, seed exchange networks, and agroecology living labs exemplify how production and exchange can be organised around principles of sufficiency, collective governance, and ecological care rather than expansion and extraction.

From a South African perspective, alternative business models must be grounded in the realities of communities navigating significant material constraints. This means supporting cooperative and community-based structures that can diversify income, add value locally, and build resilience without requiring communities to adopt conventional growth-oriented firm models. Embedding these alternatives within enabling policy frameworks — including access to land, finance, and markets — is a precondition for their viability.

From an Ecuadorian perspective, the most instructive examples are hybrid organisational forms that combine community governance with selective market engagement, allowing communities to diversify income and add local value while retaining territorial control and avoiding subordination to external market imperatives. More broadly, sufficiency-oriented business models — in which value creation remains territorially embedded, production follows ecological cycles, exchange is organised through fair pricing and local value addition, and surpluses serve the reproduction of life rather than expansion — offer a concrete institutional expression of post-development alternatives to growth-centred paradigms.

Taken together, these four recommendations point toward a governance approach that is plural and context sensitive. Rather than promoting uniform solutions, a post-development perspective supports governance approaches that are more sensitive to territorial specificities and to the plurality of wellbeing trajectories. It also strengthens the capacity of public policy to respond to diverse contexts of transformation. The Ecuadorian experiences are particularly instructive in this regard: they demonstrate that sustainable wellbeing can be organised entirely outside the hegemonic growth paradigm that dominates much of the European and global policy debate, challenging the assumption that this axis represents the only or inevitable reference point for sustainability transitions. Ultimately, the case invites policymakers to move toward governance approaches that recognise coexistence, embrace diversity, and support multiple pathways toward sustainable wellbeing.

For European decision-makers, the added value of these experiences lies in their contribution to designing policies that recognise and actively manage the coexistence of multiple pathways – governance approaches more sensitive to territorial specificity, institutional diversity, and the plurality of wellbeing trajectories. For South African practitioners, they reinforce the importance of grounding alternative initiatives in community realities, legitimate institutions, and long-term relational commitment. Ultimately, all three contexts together invite policymakers to move toward governance that embraces diversity, sustains difference, and supports multiple routes toward sustainable wellbeing.

3. Towards post-growth in Europe: government-led initiatives

Various actors and strategies will have to work together to foster post-growth transformations (Brand et al., 2020; Smith et al., 2021; Wright, 2010, 2019). The state could be one important actor among others to implement post-growth policies on the societal scale (D’Alisa & Kallis, 2020; Koch, 2020). However, in postgrowth literature change “from within” is most often assumed to be reformist, incremental and non-radical, contrary to bottom-up mobilisation and external pressures which are understood as enabling radical changes. To understand how the transformative potential of government initiatives could be strengthened, we asked, what are the barriers and drivers for post-growth leaning government initiatives? Which strategies do public officials employ to strengthen post-growth approaches in policymaking? Which language and arguments do public officials find most useful to support post-growth approaches?

We use post-growth as an umbrella term for a variety of growth-critical visions of societal transformation, including degrowth, the wellbeing economy and Doughnut economics (Gerber & Raina, 2018; Kallis et al., 2025). There are various post-growth leaning government initiatives in Europe and beyond aiming to foster post-growth approaches in policymaking. These initiatives include Wellbeing Economy Governments on the national and regional scale as well as Doughnut economics initiatives which operate predominantly on the local level (DEAL, 2024; Hough-Stewart & Janoo, 2024). For example, the National Assembly for Wales adopted the Future Generations Act in 2015, obliging public bodies to take their decisions in line with future generations’ wellbeing (Messham & Sheard, 2020; Welsh Government, n.d.). Many local governments across the world have adopted a Doughnut economics framework to measure performance, steer decision-making or to foster internal, procedural changes (Grcheva & Vianello, 2025). However, so far, the transformative character of post-growth leaning government initiatives has been limited due to structural barriers and risks of cooptation (Angresius et al., 2025; Hayden, 2025; Mason & Büchs, 2023).

To understand how post-growth approaches in policymaking could be fostered in Europe, we collected qualitative data in three steps. First, we interviewed 34 individuals working with Wellbeing Economy

Governments and Doughnut Economics initiatives in 13 Global North countries. The interviews focused on the barriers and enablers the initiatives face. Second, we interviewed 54 post-growth-minded individuals from 7 European countries working in or with governments about the strategies that they employ to foster post-growth approaches in policymaking. Third, based on the interview findings, we conducted an online workshop with 19 participants (mostly recruited from our previous interviewees) to inquire which types of frames and arguments they find most useful for promoting post-growth policy approaches. In all of our empirical work, study participants included civil servants, elected officials, civil society actors and academics working on local, regional, national and EU governance scales. The data collections took place online between November 2023 and November 2025. Our findings, together with a literature review on barriers, enablers and strategies for post-growth approaches, informed the PESTEL analysis of barriers and drivers for post-growth approaches in policymaking in Europe (Table 2).

Table 2. PESTEL analysis of barriers and drivers for post-growth approaches in policymaking in Europe.

PESTEL dimension	Key Barriers	Key Drivers	Policy and Practice Recommendations
Political	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Powerful opposing actors • Supportive government loses power • Lack of coherence across frameworks • Short-term thinking • Dominant use of GDP as an indicator 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Crises creating political momentum • Pressure from social movements and civil society actors • Key individuals and high-level political support 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Building alliances between actors in- and outside of government • Participatory governance approaches • Broad and agreeable framing of post-growth concepts • Alternative measurement metrics and decision-making tools
Economic	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Growth dependencies in the global economic system • Perceived dependence of social spending on economic growth • Lack of structural funding for post-growth initiatives within government 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Underperforming economic outcomes 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Advocate policies that detach basic needs provisioning from profit-driven (market) provisioning • Reform taxation towards wealth stocks to promote redistribution • Support workers cooperatives and not-for-profit organisations

Social	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Pro-growth discourses and cultural entrenchment of growth paradigm • Lack of openness for change 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Lived experiences of non-growth dependent provisioning systems 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Awareness raising • Positive and hopeful framings of post-growth futures • Aim to improve citizens' lived experiences through policy changes
Technological	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Path dependencies of fossil infrastructures • Technological innovation driven by profit motive and growth incentives • Lack of democratic control over technological innovation 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Development of open-source technologies • Examples of community-driven innovation 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Democratise technological developments and R&I investments
Environmental	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Understanding of nature as a commodity/of humans as external to nature 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ecological crises 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Communicate scientific evidence of urgency of ecological crises
Legal	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Siloed organisation of government • Lack of legally enforceable wellbeing and ecological objectives 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Positive examples post-growth aligned legal frameworks, e.g. Rights for Nature and Future Generations Acts 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Enshrining prioritisation of ecological and wellbeing objectives in long-term legislative frameworks

The PESTEL analysis points to the structural embeddedness of the growth paradigm in mental and material infrastructures as a cross-cutting barrier. In addition, a lack of coherence across places and frameworks and siloed ways of working hinder the consolidation of efforts. In contrast, building broad alliances to foster political pressure and ensure coherence in the discourses of post-growth proponents could increase the overall political pressure. Ecological, economic and political crises can act as windows of opportunity to build political support, introduce policy changes and enshrine ecological and well-being objectives in long-term legislative frameworks. Moreover, best practice examples and small-scale initiatives showcasing alternative ways of needs provisioning in sustainable ways could strengthen post-growth positions.

Crosscutting policy recommendations for government-led initiatives in Europe

POLICY RECOMMENDATION 1: Build broad alliances

Build alliances with a broad range of institutional and non-institutional actors supporting growth-critical approaches. Start from common ground, linking proposals to widely shared challenges and focus on redefining widely shared objectives in non-growth-oriented ways. Especially for elected officials: aim for coherent lines of argumentation and language over time, across strategies and frameworks.

Key actors:

- Elected officials building alliances across party lines and with a variety of stakeholders in their constituency
- Civil servants looking for like-minded civil servants within their institutions
- Civil servants actively seeking out collaborations with civil society actors and academics who can bring openly critical positions to policymaking

POLICY RECOMMENDATION 2: Make strategies as concrete and context specific as possible

Speak to local realities and lived experiences of citizens with concrete policy proposals. Encourage a diversity of alternative economic approaches and engage in diverse discourses that suit specific contexts and audiences.

Key actors:

- Elected officials explain how specific problems in their constituency could be addressed from a post-growth perspective

POLICY RECOMMENDATION 3: Focus on hopeful framings

Use forward-looking framings and metaphors to describe post-growth approaches and futures as viable alternatives to growth-focused imaginations of wellbeing.

Key actors:

- Elected officials focus post-growth aligned political programs on how citizens' lives would be improved
- Civil servants frame projects around broadly appealing, hopeful concepts such as the “wellbeing economy” or “the good life”

POLICY RECOMMENDATION 4: *Look for ways to strengthen growth-critical discourses*

Openly criticize economic growth when appropriate and fruitful or look for ways to strengthen and collaborate with actors who are in a position to do so, e.g. civil society actors, elected officials or journalists.

Key actors:

- Elected officials shaping parliamentary debates and political discussions
- Journalists giving a voice (or not) to growth-critical positions in the media

POLICY RECOMMENDATION 5: *Encourage participatory governance approaches*

Shifting decision-making power to citizens could facilitate the implementation of post-growth approaches which might not be favoured by established institutional actors. In addition, experiences of political engagement might encourage citizens to demand greater democratization in other spheres of life as well, for example, through worker cooperatives.

Key actors:

- Elected officials advocating for participatory governance
- Citizens pressuring for greater influence and taking part in political decision-making

4. Towards post-growth food systems: examples from Europe and South Africa

While food systems are crucial for socio-ecological well-being, they are less discussed in the literature on sustainable well-being¹. Although not originally planned in the project proposal, we decided, driven by empirical case studies in South Africa, to adopt a food system focus to investigate often abstract, complex and systemic concepts of sustainability transition and wellbeing in more concrete contexts.

We focus on sustainable wellbeing and food systems for four interconnected reasons. First, the long history of economic development shows that the shift from agrarian to industrial and post-industrial societies was built on transforming food production. Land reforms, technological change, and new labour and investment policies gradually displaced people from the land and into industrial work (Lewis, 1954; Storm, 2015; Kalecki; Cramer, Di John and Sender, 2022). This process — often described as structural transformation — drove the Green Revolution and gave rise to the industrialised, high-input agricultural systems we see today. Crucially, this transformation was not natural or inevitable: it was politically constructed, and its costs and benefits were unevenly distributed, both within and between countries. In the Global South, these dynamics shaped deep dependencies in food trade and supply chains that persist to this day, with many lower-income countries remaining locked into producing commodities for export while relying on imports for basic food needs.

Second, Polanyi (1944) showed that the rise of market economies was inseparable from the enclosure of common lands and the displacement of rural communities. This process gradually severed economic life from its social and ecological roots — what Polanyi called disembedding — and set in motion patterns of ecological extraction that continue to define industrial agriculture. As Manolchev et al. (2024) put it, industrialising food production radically shifted not only how economies are organised but also humanity's relationship to nature and the planet.

Third, food is a basic human need. Access to healthy and nutritious food is fundamental to wellbeing, and its absence is a direct source of poverty, poor health, and human suffering (Büchs and Koch, 2017). This is not equally distributed: food insecurity remains concentrated in regions and communities that have historically been disadvantaged by the very trade structures and development pathways described above.

Fourth, the global food system is now a primary driver of environmental breakdown. Industrial food production accounts for roughly one-third of all greenhouse gas emissions, and over 38% of the world's

¹ Scopus search results in December 2025 for “food systems” AND “sustainable-wellbeing” results in 0 results, while “food system*” AND “post\$growth” OR “de\$growth” OR “sustainable well\$being” results in 20 results. This is an indication of the novelty of the field.

land surface has been converted to agricultural use, driving deforestation and biodiversity loss (te Wierik et al., 2025). These pressures are self-undermining: environmental degradation worsens the climatic conditions on which agriculture itself depends (Feola, 2025). Addressing food systems is therefore not a peripheral concern but central to any serious attempt to stay within planetary boundaries.

It is important for agrifood transformations to be increasingly recognised in post-growth literature (Raina and Kachroo, 2024; Chakori et al., 2026; Feola, 2025; Manolchev et al., 2024; McGreevy et al., 2022). Food systems point to different features of producing and distribution of food. This encompasses food production, business and trade, culture and governance (McGreevy et al., 2022). Transformations in this sense are understood not as a “mere reduction of consumption, but a qualitative change that can be even considered an improvement with respect to the satisfaction of human needs, given the improved nutritional composition of the dietary shift” (Bodirsky et al., 2021, p. 344). This would require a socio-economic transformation towards sufficiency, regeneration, localised, communally embedded food production (McGreevy et al., 2022; Feola, 2025; Chakori et al., 2026). Business models are based on cooperative and community-scale trusts, and commons. Furthermore, the understanding of sustainable technology for food production changes. Post-growth argues for resource-saving technologies rather than labour-saving technologies, leading to higher employment and reducing the use of energy and materials in production. Hence, post-growth transformations are argued to need a shift towards agroecological and regenerative practices, and selective use of technology, and mostly relying on simple technology. (Feola, 2025; Manolchev et al., 2024.)

Yet another important concept, i.e., food governance, emphasises cross-sectoral, multi-level and -actor system governance (McGreevy et al., 2022). In relation to transformation governance, Feola (2025) distinguishes three pathways to food system transformations: *evolutionary policy approach*, *synergies in political strategies* and *social movement coalitions*. In the evolutionary policy approach actors such as alternative food networks, co-operatives play an important role in food system transformations as prefigurative actors, setting an example on alternative food production. In evolutionary policies, such actors are leveraged through creating spaces and allocating resources, while deliberately phasing out unsustainable and unjust farming. Synergy strategies between alternative market actors, food sharing initiatives, local communities and their networks, as well as researchers, and policy makers are important to leverage change. Finally, social movement coalitions aim to create alliances across social movements to put pressure on policymakers to achieve desired changes, usually locally and nationally. (Feola, 2025.)

4.1 Post-growth and agrifood in Europe

The European food system of today is characterised by stark inequalities, environmental degradation and unhealthy diets. In the EU, agriculture is responsible for 11% of GHG emissions. Some agricultural

practices have contributed significantly to biodiversity loss and soil and water degradation¹. Farmers account for only 4.2 % of the total EU workforce and of these 8.7 million people, less than 12 % are younger than 40 years old². Yet the Common Agricultural Policy (CAP) is one of the main parts of the EU budget, making up around 31% of the total Multiannual Financial Framework (MFF)³.

The long-term resiliency and sustainability of the European food system are at risk. As a response, post-growth literature suggests building the agrifood system on sufficiency, regeneration, distribution, commons and care (McGreevy et al., 2022). In practice, this means shifting from large energy and matter-intensive farms to smaller scale farms practising agroecology and permaculture. Post-growth builds on long-term discussions stemming from agroecology and food sovereignty discussions (Roman-Alcalá, 2017; Pixová et al., 2025). A lot of policy work has already been done in these perspectives, for example, by the Via Campesina movement and food sovereignty movements.

The food system is a multi-level system encompassing a whole spectrum of actors from production to distribution, i.e., farmers, distributors, retailers, consumers, and policymakers. To gain insight into drivers and barriers of transformation in Europe, we organised two policy labs in Europe in collaboration with the European Policy Centre. The first policy lab took place in Brussels on June 10, 2025, and the second one was held online on October 29, 2025. Both workshops lasted around 2 hours. In total, 20 participants joined from civil society organisations, EU policy institutions, start-ups, research and industry (see Appendix 1 for details of the workshops).

Based on the workshop discussions on post-growth and agrifood perspectives, contemporary food system debates reveal a governance landscape dominated by pro-business priorities, short-term productivity imperatives, and entrenched corporate interests that collectively obstruct meaningful structural transformation. Politically, long-term planning remains absent, localised food production is routinely dismissed as inefficient, and alternative framings — centred on food sovereignty, the recognition of diverse agricultural practices, and the reorientation of instruments such as the CAP and the Green Deal toward ecosystem health and soil regeneration — struggle to gain institutional traction. Economically, centralised value chains and power asymmetries reinforce profit-driven market logics that even restrict cooperative practices such as the solidary exchange of seeds. Counterstrategies emphasise localising production, scaling not-for-profit models, expanding public procurement, and incentivising shorter supply chains through support for community-supported agriculture, food hubs, and cooperative structures, with the aim of rebalancing power and strengthening local economies.

Socially, public understanding of food system concentration remains shallow, farming continues to carry low social status, and media landscapes largely reproduce agribusiness framings. This sustains a productivity-first consensus that marginalises agroecological alternatives and fuels polarisation. Transformative pathways call for shifting consumption norms from quantity toward quality, restoring social respect for farming, engaging new generations of practitioners, and deploying media strategies

¹ [https://www.europarl.europa.eu/RegData/etudes/BRIE/2023/751395/EPRS_BRI\(2023\)751395_EN.pdf](https://www.europarl.europa.eu/RegData/etudes/BRIE/2023/751395/EPRS_BRI(2023)751395_EN.pdf) (accessed 27.3.2026)

² [Farmers and the agricultural labour force - statistics - Statistics Explained - Eurostat](#) (accessed 26.3.2026)

³ [CAP funds - Agriculture and rural development - European Commission](#) (accessed 26.3.2026)

capable of reshaping dominant mindsets. Technologically, agricultural innovation remains captured by efficiency-driven, extractive models that deepen inequalities and sideline regenerative and traditional knowledge systems. A more equitable trajectory requires democratising access to open-source tools, investing in peer-to-peer learning and seed exchange networks, embedding precautionary principles in technological governance, and redirecting public funding — through the CAP, the Green Deal, and research programmes — away from productivity-maximising agribusiness technologies and toward low-input, circular farming systems.

Ecologically, the intensification of climate pressures, the persistence of monocultures, and continued reliance on chemical inputs underscore the urgency of diversified, shorter value chains governed by strict pollution standards. Legally, anti-trust frameworks remain inadequate, cooperative economic models receive limited regulatory recognition, and seed-market concentration continues largely unchecked. Addressing these structural conditions requires robust competition law reform, trade regulations that promote agrobiodiversity over corporate dominance, and public procurement and marketing rules designed to actively support sustainable producers. Taken together, these political, economic, social, technological, ecological, and legal dimensions, summarised in Table 3, constitute an interlocking set of challenges whose transformation demands coordinated, multi-actor intervention across governance scales.

Table 3. PESTEL and post-growth-related policy recommendations in the agrifood

PESTEL dimension	Key Barriers	Key Drivers	Policy and Practice Recommendations
Political	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Lack of a long-term plan for agricultural transformation Food system politics are pro-business Emphasis on productivity and maximum yield Geopolitical situation Localised food production is seen as inefficient, idealistic and romantic 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Understanding food as a human right, not a commodity Political and corporate will to change the status quo Local-level community initiatives on food Multi-actor policy platforms 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Making visible how centralised the current system is via media campaigns Ensuring that diverse agricultural practices are recognised and valued in the Green Deal and the CAP Shift CAP incentives away from yield maximisation toward ecosystem care, soil health, and food sovereignty Tripartite negotiations on agrifood transformations

<p>Economic</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Centralised value chains and power imbalances • Strong vested interests • Profit-incentive • Market interest and prohibition of the solidarity exchange of seeds 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Localising food production • Scaling out not-for-profit businesses • Higher due diligence for retailers • Polluter pays principle • Connecting local food networks, producers and retailers 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Public procurement of local food • Incentivise shorter supply chains via increased domestic production (e.g. use subsidy systems directed at those building CSA models, food hubs, etc) • Setting up a network of forerunners and willing to leverage sustainable practices (e.g. CSAs, retailers and consumers, and providing entry points for them in governance) • Creating digital food platforms to link producers and consumers • Policy support for cooperative structures • Support access to land for young farmers • Providing marketplaces for small farmers in cities/municipalities • Retailers to support farmers in the diversified cultivation of crops
<p>Social</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Lack of awareness of the centralised nature of the current food system • Farming is seen as backward • Lack of social security for farmers • Media represents agribusiness interest • Agroecology is seen as inefficient 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Valuing health over productivity • Consumption habits from quantity to quality • Valuing farming • Engaging more young farmers and community building 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Changing mindsets on food systems through media campaigns • Engaging critical media with food systems change • Supportive social policies for affordable living (housing, health, social safety net) • Food social security policies

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Persistence of productivity thinking • Polarization 		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Create platforms where producers can exchange best practices
Technological	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Technological development focuses on efficiency gains and extractivism rather than regeneration • High-tech focus can exacerbate existing inequalities 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Recognise the value of traditional knowledge • Social innovation, democratic, accessible, open-source technology • Using a combination of ancestral and modern technology • Accessibility of technology to de-intensify the concentration of market power • Seed exchange between farmers • Integrating biodiverse knowledge into education programs 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Expand peer-to-peer learning platforms (e.g. Organic Farm Knowledge) with a focus on collective sufficiency, not competitive advantage • Digital food platforms • Precautionary principles and RRI on technology development • Funding for social innovation, democratic, accessible open-source technology in CAP and Green Deal • Funding research that explores low-input circular farming systems rather than technologies that mainly serve agribusiness productivity • Higher education programs towards more sustainable practices and tools • Building agroecology living labs as commons-based infrastructures with open access to knowledge rather than proprietary growth-driven innovations
Environmental	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Limited space in cities for urban farming • Climate change 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Restrictions on the use of pesticides and chemical inputs • Shifting from monocrops to diversified production • Shorter value chains 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Limits to market actors on pollution levels • Restrictions on the use of pesticides and chemical inputs • Implementing standards and quality criteria that support the diversity of knowledge

<p>Legal</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Anti-trust laws are not effective in the seed market • Regulatory framework is not supportive of post-growth visions 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Recognising cooperative models • Stringent environmental regulations 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Anti-trust and competition laws on seeds address the concentration of control in the seed market, promoting fair competition and diversity. • Trade and international trade regulations ensure fair trade practices that support agrobiodiverse systems. • Public procurement policies leverage government purchasing power to support sustainable practices. • Marketing laws regulate advertising to promote agrobiodiverse systems.
---------------------	---	---	---

Crosscutting policy recommendations for post-growth and agrifood in Europe

POLICY RECOMMENDATION 1: Reframing food not as a commodity, but as a human right

Many people do not have access to healthy and nutritious food. Food should be recognised as a human right.

POLICY RECOMMENDATION 2: Reframing competitiveness as quality and resilience

Food systems are characterised by growth- and efficiency-driven mindsets. This perpetuates extractivist farming practices that are unstable and vulnerable to shocks. Competitiveness is enhanced by resilient food systems.

POLICY RECOMMENDATION 3: *Funding for social innovation, democratic, accessible and open-source technology for agroecology*

To enable spill-overs of best practices and knowledge on farming practices, the Common Agricultural Policy (CAP) and Green Deal should include funding for social innovation and open-source technologies.

POLICY RECOMMENDATION 4: *Multi-level and polycentric governance through food councils at the city, town and regional level to support relocalisation of food systems*

Tripartite negotiations to set policy goals and agreements on food system transformations. Setting up a multi-stakeholder group to bring together citizens, producers, NGOs, and government to influence food system policies.

POLICY RECOMMENDATION 5: *Ensuring farmers' basic income and social security through affordable housing, health and social safety nets*

Many farmers, especially small-scale grassroots, face insecurities and challenges due to the highly concentrated food system. Providing basic services and a social safety net helps in transforming farming practices.

POLICY RECOMMENDATION 6: *Restrictions on the use of pesticides and chemical inputs*

Scaling down unecological and socially unsustainable farming mechanisms through regulation and restrictions is needed.

POLICY RECOMMENDATION 7: *Shifting current agricultural policies from yield-maximisation to sufficiency, resiliency and regeneration*

Shift the Common Agricultural Policy (CAP) incentives away from yield maximisation toward ecosystem care, soil health, and food sovereignty.

4.2 Green growth and agrifood in South Africa

The legacy of apartheid is still felt in South Africa's development today, particularly in the uneven distribution of resources and infrastructure across the country. This legacy also makes the South African food system highly contested, underpinning a dualistic agrarian system (Kushitor et al., 2022). Regardless of South Africa's high per capita income for a developing country and its national food security (van Huyssteen et al., 2023), the country faces a higher burden of malnutrition than countries of comparable income levels and is undergoing a nutrition and epidemiological transition. Social, economic, and ecological factors lead to between 23–30% of the population having severely inadequate access to food or being at risk of hunger.

Like many developed and developing countries, South Africa's policy agenda relies on green transition. Together, recent policy frameworks signal a strategic alignment of agriculture with climate and sustainability objectives. For example:

- The Climate Change Act legally mandates climate integration across sectors, meaning agricultural planning and food systems must account for climate risks and emissions.
- The Agriculture and Agro-processing Master Plan (AAMP) provides a sector roadmap for sustainable transformation and resilience.
- The Food and Nutrition Security Plan embeds sustainability into food production and access strategies.
- The Science, Technology and Innovation (STI) Roadmap links innovation, technology, and inclusive growth with environmental sustainability.

These policies collectively move South Africa's agrifood systems toward a green growth model—one that balances productivity, climate resilience, ecosystem stewardship, and equitable participation in markets and value chains.

Part of the innovation and technology policies that promote sustainable technologies is the Science, Technology and Innovation (STI) Roadmap for Agriculture, led by the Department of Science, Technology and Innovation (DSTI) in partnership with the Food and Agriculture Organization (FAO) of the United Nations. This roadmap, anchored in the country's STI Decadal Plan (2022–2032) and the 2019 STI White Paper, aims to integrate sustainable technologies into agricultural value chains to strengthen productivity, climate resilience, and competitiveness. It emphasises systemic innovation — such as digital decision-support tools, precision agriculture, early-warning systems, plant and animal improvement technologies, and agro-processing innovations — that contribute to more efficient, resilient, and inclusive food systems. Recent South African social policy frameworks increasingly integrate food security, rural livelihoods, and environmental sustainability within a broader green transition agenda for agrifood systems. The Department of Agriculture, Land Reform and Rural Development, through the National Food and Nutrition Security Plan (2024–2029), links the right to food

with sustainable local production, smallholder inclusion, and climate-resilient practices. Complementary programmes such as the Comprehensive Rural Development Programme align land reform and rural regeneration with sustainable land use and community-based agricultural enterprises. Together, these policies reposition agrifood systems as both a social protection mechanism and a sustainability lever, embedding environmental stewardship within poverty reduction and food access strategies.

In parallel, employment-based social interventions such as the Department of Public Works and Infrastructure's Expanded Public Works Programme increasingly incorporate green economy principles by supporting ecosystem restoration, climate-smart infrastructure, and sustainable agriculture initiatives. By linking income support, skills development, and local procurement for feeding schemes to environmentally responsible production, social policy instruments create demand for sustainable food while strengthening rural resilience. Collectively, these measures demonstrate an integrated approach in which social inclusion, climate adaptation, and agrifood system transformation reinforce one another within South Africa's emerging green transition framework.

South African agricultural policy, in turn, increasingly embeds green growth principles by aligning productivity, climate resilience, and sustainability across sector strategies. Core frameworks such as the Climate Change Act (2024) mandate climate integration across economic sectors, including agriculture, while the Agriculture and Agro-processing Master Plan (AAMP) promotes innovation, market inclusion, and resilience to environmental shocks. Complementing these are the National Food and Nutrition Security Plan (2024–2029) and strategic initiatives on climate-smart agriculture and rural transformation, which together prioritise sustainable production practices, resource-efficient technologies, and equitable access to markets for smallholder farmers. Innovation agendas, including the STI Roadmap for Agriculture, further support the adoption of digital tools and sustainable technologies, collectively positioning the agricultural sector to balance economic growth with environmental stewardship and social inclusion.

Although South Africa favours green growth policies, its society and culture are highly influenced by a philosophy of Ubuntu, emphasising collectivism and a community approach. Because of Ubuntu's influence, South African society has characteristics of post-growth or even post-development, not purely characterising a green growth economy. This tension between different growth views is present in grassroots initiatives that are driven by local actors, networks and community groups and emphasise place-based and bottom-up solutions.

4.2.1 Policy recommendations for grassroots -driven green growth

For the South African case study, we investigated two agrifood grassroots innovations in rural and urban contexts (for closer details, see Herselman & Mahwai, 2025). The case study was performed in 2024–2025, and it integrated 20 interviewees in group or individual interviews and engaged 58 workshop

participants who focused on identifying and agreeing on key change factors in agrifood sustainability transition. See a description of the South African research process in Appendix 2. Table 4 summarises key drivers and barriers and suggests policy and practice recommendations derived from the case research.

Table 4. PESTEL analysis of South African agrifood cases

PESTEL Dimension	Key Barriers	Key Drivers	Policy and Practice Recommendations
Political	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Policy–implementation gaps at the local government level • Limited institutional recognition of informal and non-market innovation • Fragmented governance and short political cycles 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • National commitments to sustainability, climate resilience, and inclusive development • Increasing policy recognition of participatory and community-based approaches • Decentralisation creates opportunities for local experimentation 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Explicitly integrate grassroots innovation into national sustainability and innovation policies • Strengthen vertical coordination across governance levels • Develop long-term policy instruments that protect grassroots niches
Economic	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Limited access to finance, credit, and insurance • Dependence on donor funding • Market pressures that risk diluting participatory and transformative values 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • High unemployment drives community entrepreneurship • Rising food, energy, and water costs create demand for local solutions • Emergence of alternative and solidarity economies 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Establish dedicated grant, micro-finance, and blended finance mechanisms • Support hybrid economic models, balancing financial viability and social goals • Recognise alternative economic practices in economic policy frameworks
Social	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Unequal participation due to gender, age, or class • Skills and capacity gaps • Risk of elite capture within communities 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Strong social capital and community networks • Indigenous and place-based knowledge systems • Ubuntu-oriented values of solidarity and collective well-being 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Prioritise inclusive participation and equity-focused interventions • Invest in community-based capacity building and peer learning • Strengthen accountability and governance mechanisms
Technological	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Limited technical support and maintenance capacity • Weak linkages with formal R&D institutions 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Availability of low-cost, modular, and appropriate technologies 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Facilitate partnerships between grassroots innovators and research institutions

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Digital divides are limiting access 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Opportunities for technological leapfrogging Digital platforms enabling knowledge sharing 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Promote open-source technologies and shared knowledge platforms Invest in technical advisory services and local infrastructure
Environmental	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Climate variability threatens initiative stability Limited access to environmental data and forecasting Regulatory barriers for small-scale initiatives 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Climate change impacts necessitating local adaptation Environmental degradation is increasing the urgency for sustainable practices Alignment with circular economy and low-carbon principles 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Integrate grassroots innovation into climate adaptation and resilience strategies Improve access to environmental data and early warning systems Develop proportionate, enabling environmental regulations
Legal / Regulatory	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Complex registration and compliance procedures Regulatory bias toward formal, large-scale enterprises Unclear intellectual property regimes for collective innovation 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Growing recognition of community rights and inclusive innovation Legal frameworks for cooperatives and social enterprises 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Simplify and update legal, regulatory and policy requirements for grassroots initiatives Create legal categories recognising informal and hybrid models Protect community intellectual property and collective knowledge

Crosscutting policy recommendations for grassroots-driven growth in South Africa

Due to our focus on grassroots initiatives—deeply shaped by *Ubuntu* as a relational ethic of solidarity, reciprocity, and collective well-being—the recommendations adopt a strong community-centred and inclusive green growth orientation. In this framing, green growth is not limited to technological upgrading or carbon efficiency; rather, it is grounded in locally embedded capabilities, social cohesion, and ecological stewardship. Grassroots innovations operate at the nexus of livelihood security, environmental regeneration, and social justice, thereby aligning economic development with sustainability transitions.

For innovation policymaking, it is therefore essential to formally recognise and strategically support these initiatives. They originate from tacit knowledge, lived experience, indigenous practices, and community-based skills that exist largely outside formal education systems and conventional research and development structures (Hossain, 2016). Yet these knowledge systems frequently generate contextually appropriate, resource-efficient, and socially legitimate solutions—particularly relevant for advancing circular economy practices, agroecology, food sovereignty, and climate resilience. In this

sense, grassroots initiatives function as distributed innovation nodes within a broader green growth ecosystem.

Moreover, grassroots innovations often surface integrative understandings of sustainability that transcend sectoral silos. Their practices simultaneously address social inclusion, environmental integrity, and economic justice, contributing to more holistic sustainability outcomes. This integrative character is especially valuable in agrifood transitions, where food security, biodiversity, local economic participation, and equitable value chains intersect.

Importantly, active citizenship embedded in grassroots innovation processes strengthens democratic institutions and participatory governance (Buenting de Almeida Rego, 2021). Through deliberative engagement, co-creation workshops, and community-led experimentation, these initiatives enhance accountability, trust, and institutional learning. They provide bottom-up intelligence that can inform social development, rural revitalisation, and green industrial policies.

Embedding grassroots innovation within green growth strategies, therefore, contributes to:

- More inclusive and place-based innovation systems;
- Enhanced socio-ecological resilience;
- Strengthened democratic governance and institutional legitimacy, and
- Just and equitable sustainability transitions.

In sum, recognising grassroots initiatives within green growth frameworks enables policy to move beyond technocratic sustainability solutions toward transformative, community-anchored development pathways.

POLICY RECOMMENDATION 1: Adopt an Ecosystem Approach

Support grassroots innovation ecosystems along sustainable technology ecosystems that integrate policy, finance, infrastructure, knowledge, and social capital to foster responsible innovation.

Key actors: The ecosystem must be understood as a multi-actor, multi-level configuration of institutions, networks, and enabling conditions. The following actors are suggested:

- Public Sector and Governance Actors: Department of Agriculture, Land Reform and Rural Development
- Grassroots and Community-Based Actors: South African National Civic Organisation
- Knowledge and Research Institutions: Council for Scientific and Industrial Research
- Financial and Investment Actors: Industrial Development Corporation
- Private Sector and Market Actors: Shoprite Holdings
- Intermediaries and Boundary-Spanning Organisations: Technology Innovation Agency

- Civil Society and Advocacy Actors: South African Local Government Association

POLICY RECOMMENDATION 2: Bridge Policy–Practice Gaps

Align policy design with local realities through co-creation, participatory governance, and iterative learning.

Key actors:

- Department of Agriculture, Land Reform and Rural Development: policy design and agricultural implementation alignment
- Department of Science and Innovation: innovation policy coordination and systems alignment
- South African Local Government Association: municipal coordination and local governance integration
- Council for Scientific and Industrial Research: evidence generation and policy support
- National Research Foundation: research funding and knowledge systems strengthening
- Industrial Development Corporation: financing mechanisms aligned with policy objectives
- Community-based organisations and cooperatives: local knowledge, participatory input, and co-creation platforms

POLICY RECOMMENDATION 3: Strengthen Intermediaries

Invest in innovation intermediaries that connect grassroots initiatives with policymakers, markets, and research institutions to integrate traditional knowledge with contemporary technological opportunities.

Key actors:

- Technology Innovation Agency: supports incubation, technology transfer, and innovation bridging
- Council for Scientific and Industrial Research: applied research and industry–community collaboration
- National Research Foundation: research funding and knowledge network support
- Industrial Development Corporation: catalytic financing and ecosystem support
- South African Local Government Association: municipal coordination and multi-stakeholder engagement
- Innovation hubs, incubators, and living labs: facilitation of co-creation and experimentation platforms

- Community-based organisations and cooperatives: linkage between local knowledge systems and formal innovation networks

Support replication, adaptation, and networked scaling rather than forced standardisation or marketisation.

Key actors to support this recommendation are:

- Department of Agriculture, Land Reform and Rural Development: policy support for inclusive agricultural scaling models
- Department of Science and Innovation: support for responsible innovation and systems-level diffusion
- Industrial Development Corporation: blended finance to enable values-aligned expansion
- Technology Innovation Agency: incubation, technology transfer, and adaptive scaling support
- National Research Foundation: funding for collaborative and community-engaged research
- Universities and universities of technology: knowledge diffusion, monitoring, and capacity development
- Cooperatives and community-based organisations: network-based replication grounded in local values
- Multi-stakeholder platforms and innovation intermediaries — coordination of adaptive, non-standardised scaling pathways

POLICY RECOMMENDATION 5: Institutionalise Learning

Embed grassroots-generated knowledge into sustainability, innovation, and development policy processes.

Key actors supporting this policy process are:

- Department of Science and Innovation: integration of evidence into national innovation policy processes
- Department of Agriculture, Land Reform and Rural Development: incorporation of community knowledge into agricultural and rural development policy
- National Research Foundation: funding mechanisms that support participatory and applied research
- Council for Scientific and Industrial Research: systems analysis and policy-relevant knowledge generation
- South African Local Government Association: municipal learning networks and policy feedback loops
- Universities and universities of technology: knowledge co-production and curriculum integration

- Community-based organisations and cooperatives: grassroots evidence generation and lived-experience insights

4.2.1.1 Key policy areas to promote grassroots-driven growth in South Africa

Across the proposed ecosystem functions bridging policy–practice gaps, strengthening intermediaries, enabling value-aligned scaling, and institutionalising learning, the key policy areas in South Africa that underpin the full set of ecosystem functions include:

- Innovation and Science Policy – Support for responsible innovation, co-creation, research–practice integration, and ecosystem-based innovation models.
- Agricultural and Agrifood Policy – Sustainable production systems, agroecology, value-chain inclusion, food security, and rural transformation.
- Rural Development and Local Economic Development Policy – Place-based development, community empowerment, cooperative development, and territorial approaches.
- Green Growth and Environmental Sustainability Policy – Climate resilience, biodiversity protection, circular economy, low-carbon transitions, and environmental governance.
- Inclusive Finance and Development Finance Policy – Blended finance mechanisms, de-risking instruments, support for SMEs and cooperatives, and impact investment frameworks.
- Small Enterprise and Entrepreneurship Policy – Support for grassroots enterprises, incubation systems, market access, and innovation-led enterprise development.
- Education, Skills, and Capacity Development Policy – TVET strengthening, lifelong learning, community-based training, and innovation skills development.
- Governance and Participatory Policy – Multi-level coordination, participatory decision-making, co-design processes, and institutional accountability.
- Technology Transfer and Commercialisation Policy – Bridging research outputs with community and market applications while preserving social and ecological values.
- Monitoring, Evaluation, and Learning (MEL) Policy Frameworks – Evidence-based policymaking, adaptive management, impact measurement, and iterative policy learning.

Together, these policy areas create the enabling conditions required to align grassroots innovation ecosystems with sustainable technology systems, responsible innovation principles, and inclusive green growth objectives.

5. Beyond growth: post-development perspectives from Ecuador

The Ecuadorian case study was situated in Indigenous and rural territories where sustainable wellbeing trajectories are not structured around economic growth, market expansion, or productive intensification. Instead, wellbeing is constructed through collective practices oriented toward material sufficiency, community cohesion, reciprocity, and relational ties with territory and nature. These characteristics resonate with post-development critiques that challenge growth-centred development paradigms and question the universality of development as a policy horizon (Escobar, 2005; Ziai, 2017).

Subsequent debates have pushed beyond this critical stance, recognising that dismantling dominant frameworks is insufficient without articulating alternatives. They have done so by drawing on the idea of the pluriverse: a horizon in which diverse ontologies, forms of knowledge, and institutional arrangements coexist that cannot be reduced to a single model of progress (Escobar, 2015; Kothari et al., 2019). Rather than proposing a new universal blueprint, this perspective helps explain why community-based wellbeing trajectories affirm situated forms of life and governance that coexist with — and at times resist — policies structured around growth and standardisation.

In the Latin American context, this pluriversal horizon finds one of its most significant concrete expressions in Sumak Kawsay — and, relatedly, in Buen Vivir¹ (Acosta, 2017, Carranza-Barona & Villalba-Eguiluz, 2026; Cuestas-Caza et al., 2024; Lang, 2022). Rooted in Indigenous worldviews of the Andean region, Sumak Kawsay proposes a substantive reorganisation of the relationships between society, economy, and nature — understood not as a resource to be exploited, but as a living system with which human communities must remain in balance (Malo Larrea et al., 2024, Bermúdez-Restrepo & Vaca-López, 2026). From this perspective, wellbeing is not conceived as the result of material accumulation or unlimited growth, but as a condition of harmony and reciprocity between people, communities, and ecosystems (Coral-Guerrero et al., 2021; Cuestas-Caza et al., 2024).

Understood in these terms, the Ecuadorian case contributes to this debate not merely as an illustration, but as empirical grounding from the Global South. These community-based trajectories are neither marginal nor residual — they represent active and enduring forms of wellbeing construction rooted in long-standing practices of territorial stewardship, relationality, and collective governance (Coral-Guerrero et al., 2021; Cuestas-Caza et al., 2024; Malo Larrea et al., 2024). In doing so, they speak directly to a gap that Northern-led debates on sustainable wellbeing have identified

¹ Although they are often used interchangeably, Sumak Kawsay and Buen Vivir are not identical concepts. While Buen Vivir has become established in academic and political debate as a broad and pluralistic concept— institutionalized in Ecuador since the 2008 Constitution—Sumak Kawsay is often claimed from indigenous perspectives as an ethical-ontological horizon rooted in specific territorial practices and in a relational understanding between community, nature, and the reproduction of life. In this sense, both can be understood as partially convergent but not equivalent expressions within contemporary debates on alternatives to development (Altmann, 2016; Chassagne, 2019; Cuestas-Caza, 2021; Inuca, 2017).

but not resolved: how to organise a space of sufficiency — bounded by social needs and ecological limits — in practice (Kallis et al., 2025; O'Neill et al., 2018). By foregrounding coexistence over convergence, and the reproduction of life over accumulation, this perspective avoids subsuming Global South experiences into analytical categories designed in different socio-political contexts — and instead contributes to a more plural and context-sensitive understanding of processes of change, facilitating dialogue with other approaches addressed in this report, such as post-growth and green growth.

Furthermore, the Ecuadorian case contributes to the broader analysis of alternative growth initiatives by illustrating how sustainable wellbeing pathways can emerge and persist outside the growth-development continuum. In this sense, it complements the South African and European perspectives and supports the identification of policy options capable of engaging with plural, territorially embedded processes of change.

Drawing on a recent review of organisational experiences and specialised literature (Bermúdez-Restrepo & Vaca-López, 2026; Cachipuendo et al., 2026; Churuchumbi, 2014; Coral-Guerrero et al., 2021; Cuestas-Caza et al., 2024; Guandinango, 2013; Inuca, 2017; Malo Larrea et al., 2024; Quick & Spartz, 2018; Vargas-Chaves, 2025), as well as on fieldwork conducted in Ecuador between 2023 and 2026 — comprising 47 in-depth interviews, three participatory workshops, and follow-up activities with community organisations and local institutions (Escobar Urbina, Bedoya & Cuestas-Caza, 2025; see also Appendix 3) — it is possible to identify four principles that structure forms of economic organisation oriented toward sufficiency under the framework of Sumak Kawsay.

- The first is biocentric relationality, which recognises that human activities are intrinsically linked to the ecosystems on which they depend. Within this framework, production decisions must respect ecological cycles and territorial boundaries.
- The second is organisational territoriality, according to which economic activities are conditioned by territorial agreements and by the ecological and cultural characteristics of the territories.
- The third corresponds to community interdependence, where economic relations are structured around networks of reciprocity, cooperation, and collective work that sustain social cohesion.
- Finally, the fourth principle is the subordination of the economy to the reproduction of life, which implies that economic production is primarily oriented toward sustaining collective wellbeing and the continuity of territories.

Taken together, these principles constitute a framework for organising collective life beyond growth, one that emerges from situated Indigenous practice and institutional experience in the Global South. This is the foundation on which the following policy recommendations stand.

5.1 Policy recommendations from a post-development and pluriversal perspective

The Ecuadorian case illustrates that the transitions toward sustainable wellbeing do not follow single or universal trajectories and cannot be fully understood through analytical frameworks that assume convergence toward a single transition horizon. Grounded in a post-development and pluriversal perspective, this case demonstrates that the diversity of wellbeing trajectories should not be treated as a problem to be resolved, but rather as a structural condition of transformative processes. Across Indigenous and rural territories, wellbeing trajectories emerge from territorially embedded practices grounded in sufficiency, collective governance, relational understandings of wellbeing, and sustained relationships with nature. These trajectories coexist with dominant policy frameworks, often under conditions of tension, negotiation, and partial recognition.

The analysis of policy sectors and the PESTEL framework further illustrates how misalignments between public policy and territorial realities generate concrete barriers for community initiatives (Table 5). These barriers are not primarily technical in nature but reflect deeper normative and institutional asymmetries regarding which forms of wellbeing, innovation, and organisation are recognised as valid. Addressing these tensions requires moving beyond sectoral and technocentric interventions toward more integrated, territorially sensitive, and reflexive policy approaches.

From a policy perspective, the Ecuadorian case underscores the importance of designing public policies capable of engaging with plurality rather than attempting to subsume it under uniform solutions. Recognising multiple wellbeing trajectories, broadening the notion of innovation, and adapting regulatory and economic instruments to scale and territory are essential steps toward more inclusive and resilient governance frameworks. Such an approach does not weaken policy coherence; rather, it strengthens it by aligning policy design with the realities of diverse socio-ecological contexts.

Table 5. PESTEL analysis of the Ecuadorian case

PESTEL dimension	Key Barriers	Key Drivers	Policy and Practice Recommendations
Political	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Partial gaps remain between policy design and territorial implementation. Participation mechanisms are often intermittent rather than sustained. Coordination between community 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Strong community organisation rooted in assemblies, cabildos, and collective decision-making. Existing alliances with universities, NGOs, cooperatives, and some public actors. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Establish sustained multi-actor territorial dialogue spaces. Strengthen participatory policy review and feedback mechanisms. Support local policy experimentation around territorial priorities.

	<p>organisations and public institutions is uneven.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Local political dynamics can, in some cases, complicate collective processes. Centralised decision-making may limit timely local institutional responses. Municipal engagement in territorial conflicts, especially around water, is not always consistent. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Internal leadership spaces involving women, youth, and families. Collective memory and territorial leadership that support organisational continuity. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Develop mediation channels for water and territorial disputes.
Economic	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Mainstream economic and financial instruments tend to privilege scale, competitiveness, and standardised growth-oriented criteria. Limited access to financing mechanisms adapted to community-based and solidarity-oriented initiatives. Unstable access to markets and continued dependence on external funding, municipal resources, or family credit. Limited infrastructure for local processing, transformation, and commercialisation. Weak accounting, administrative, and commercial management capacities. Export barriers, debt burdens, and unresolved labour-related costs constrain organisational sustainability. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Small-scale community economies oriented to sufficiency, local provisioning, and territorial continuity. Productive diversification and value-added community production. Direct commercialisation strategies that reduce intermediaries and increase local revenues. Community enterprises, microenterprises, and tourism-based income strategies. Certified or differentiated production that strengthens local economic autonomy. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Create scale- and territory-sensitive credit and seed-funding windows. Support local processing, storage, and commercialisation infrastructure. Provide long-term accounting, administrative, and market access support. Strengthen fair commercialisation channels that increase direct community revenues.

<p>Social</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Relational, communal, and territorial notions of wellbeing are often overlooked by individualistic or economic policy frameworks. • Limited recognition of social reproduction and care work as foundational to territorial continuity. • Youth migration and weak generational renewal undermine long-term collective agency. • Training and technical education are often insufficiently grounded in territorial realities. • Community disinterest or uneven participation can weaken organisational renewal. • External support for long-term community capacity-building is often intermittent. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Strong community cohesion and collective work practices such as <i>minka</i>. • Local governance through assemblies, cabildos, and community organisations. supports collective agency. • Social reproduction, family networks, and care relations sustain continuity over time. • Active participation of women and youth strengthens community processes. • Strong sense of belonging and territorial identity reinforces collective action 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Recognise community cohesion, care, and social reproduction in policy design and evaluation. • Support territorially grounded training and intergenerational learning pathways. • Invest in youth leadership and women’s participation in community initiatives. • Strengthen long-term community capacity-building linked to local livelihoods.
<p>Technological</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Innovation policies remain biased toward standardised, tech-centric solutions. • Community-designed or non-technocentric innovations receive limited recognition and support. • Technology adoption is constrained when not co-designed with local actors. • Some technical solutions are poorly adapted to ecological, cultural, and territorial conditions. • Technical accompaniment is often 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Appropriate technologies are already embedded in productive and resource-management practices. • Local knowledge and ancestral practices shape technology use and adaptation. • Innovation is understood broadly, including social, organisational, and institutional forms. • Community actors are willing to combine technical tools with territorial knowledge. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Fund co-designed appropriate technology pilots in real territorial settings. • Recognise social, organisational, and institutional innovation in support programs. • Provide long-term technical accompaniment for locally adapted solutions. • Support community-led experimentation in processing, water management, and traceability.

	<p>discontinuous, short-term, or externally driven.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Limited access to technologies for processing, traceability, and productive improvement. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Existing local experimentation supports learning-by-doing and adaptation. 	
Environmental	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Persistent conflicts over water sources and uneven local governmental support. Weak institutional recognition of community-led conservation and resource-management practices. Pressures associated with intensive or extractive models that threaten forests, biodiversity, water, and territorial continuity. Weak generational continuity in ecological knowledge and care practices. Environmental education and public support mechanisms are not always grounded in local cosmovisions and territorial realities. Limited local capacities and sustained accompaniment for community-based environmental management. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Strong linkage between community wellbeing, territory, and nature. Community management of water, land, seeds, forests, and biodiversity as a core pillar of collective wellbeing and territorial sustainability. Chakras, seed conservation, reforestation, agroecological fairs, and sustainable water management practices. Sustainability is understood as an integral practice that connects production, conservation, and cultural reproduction. Ancestral ecological knowledge and reciprocity with Pachamama strengthen resilience and long-term territorial care. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Recognise community stewardship as a strategic component of water, land, and biodiversity governance. Support participatory monitoring, territorial observatories, and community-based environmental mapping. Fund locally grounded conservation, restoration, and agroecological management programs. Strengthen intercultural environmental education and alliances that secure generational continuity in territorial care.
Legal	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Administrative and regulatory requirements can be difficult for community organisations to navigate. Requirements such as e-invoicing may create 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Existing collective governance structures with internal legitimacy. Community norms and internal decision-making practices are already in operation. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Introduce more flexible compliance pathways for community organisations. Provide legal and administrative accompaniment for tax and labour procedures.

	<p>additional commercialisation challenges.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Formal procedures are not always well suited to collective and small-scale realities. • Public support frameworks remain limited for some community-based initiatives. • Legal and administrative demands can absorb time and organisational capacity. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Prior experience navigating formal and informal institutional arrangements. • Strategic alliances can facilitate engagement with public agencies and support institutions. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Simplify key procedures for small-scale territorial initiatives. • Better adapt commercialisation rules to collective forms of production.
--	--	---	---

Crosscutting policy recommendations for post-development in Ecuador

The Ecuadorian case highlights that public policies oriented toward sustainable wellbeing must go beyond the incorporation of new instruments or technologies and critically reassess the underlying assumptions that shape their design and implementation. In particular, it shows that many policy limitations stem not from technical shortcomings, but from normative frameworks that implicitly privilege growth-oriented, standardised, and scalable models of development (Escobar, 2018; Kothari et al., 2019).

The recommendations presented below emerge from fieldwork in territories, analysis of local socio-ecological initiatives, participatory dialogues developed in the policy lab, and ongoing dialogue with academic literature on the conceptual framework of Sumak Kawsay. Taken together, these recommendations seek to identify public policy guidelines that will strengthen responses to sustainability challenges based on the territorial realities of the Global South.

POLICY RECOMMENDATION 1: Co-creation: opening up policy design to territorial actors

The evidence gathered shows a persistent gap between public policy formulation and the territorial dynamics where these policies are implemented. Although participation mechanisms exist, they tend to be ad hoc or consultative, which limits their ability to significantly influence policy design. To reduce

this gap, it is necessary to move towards mechanisms that allow for the continuous participation of territorial organisations, local governments, academia, and civil society in the design and evaluation of public policies related to sustainability, territorial development, and natural resource management. One concrete way to do this is to promote permanent spaces for interaction, such as multi-stakeholder platforms or public policy laboratories, which function as collective learning environments where territorial knowledge can feed back into policy formulation and adjustment processes.

Key actors:

- National government (e.g. Ministry of Environment and Energy; Ministry of Agriculture, Livestock and Fisheries; Ministry of Production, Foreign Trade and Investments; National Planning Secretariat)
- Local governments (e.g. Municipality of Cotacachi; Municipality of Tena; and, Association of Ecuadorian Municipalities)
- Indigenous federations (e.g. Union of Peasant and Indigenous Organisations of Cotacachi — UNORCAC; Confederation of Indigenous Nationalities of Ecuador — CONAIE)
- International development organisations with field presence (e.g. Italian-Ecuadorian Fund for Sustainable Development — FIEDS; PLAN International; United Nations Development Programme — UNDP Ecuador; German International Cooperation — GIZ Ecuador)

POLICY RECOMMENDATION 2: *Territorial innovation: Recognising and supporting solutions that emerge from territories*

Fieldwork and the policy lab showed that many responses to socio-environmental challenges are already emerging from communities, local organisations, and territorial networks. However, these initiatives often remain invisible within public policy frameworks. Sustainability policies could be strengthened through mechanisms that identify, highlight, and support territorial innovations, recognising them as legitimate sources of learning and socio-ecological transformation. This may include seed funding programs, technical support for local initiatives, and platforms for exchange between territories, allowing lessons learned to be scaled up without losing their local character.

Key actors:

- Community-based and indigenous organisations (e.g. Kallari Association; Women's Central Committee of UNORCAC)
- Environmental and territorial civil society organisations (e.g. Ecological Action; Maquita Foundation)

- Indigenous-focused savings and credit cooperatives (e.g. United Women Savings and Credit Cooperative — CACMU; Atuntaqui Savings and Credit Cooperative; Mushuc Runa Savings and Credit Cooperative)
- International development banks and cooperation agencies (e.g. Inter-American Development Bank — IDB; Italian-Ecuadorian Fund for Sustainable Development — FIEDS)
- Universities and applied research centres (e.g. National Polytechnic School — EPN; University of the Americas — UDLA; Latin American Faculty of Social Sciences — FLACSO Ecuador; Central University of Ecuador; Ikiam Regional Amazonian University; Yachay Tech University)

POLICY RECOMMENDATION 3: *Territorial knowledge: Integrating local knowledge into public information systems*

Public policies are often based primarily on technical information produced at the national or sectoral level. While these information systems are essential, they often fail to capture practices, knowledge, and territorial dynamics that are relevant to resource management and productive activities. Integrating territorial knowledge and community experiences into public information systems can improve the relevance and effectiveness of policies. This can be achieved through tools such as territorial observatories, social mapping processes, participatory monitoring systems, or mechanisms for documenting local experiences, which complement official data with situated knowledge.

Key actors:

- National environmental and biodiversity information institutions (e.g. Ministry of Environment and Energy; National Institute of Biodiversity — INABIO; National Institute of Statistics and Census — INEC).
- Indigenous organisations with multidimensional territorial monitoring systems (e.g. Kichwa People of Rukullakta — PKR; Confederation of Indigenous Nationalities of the Ecuadorian Amazon — CONFENIAE; Waorani Nationality of Ecuador — NAWE).
- Civil society organisations specialised in territorial data and monitoring (e.g. EcoCiencia Foundation).
- Universities and research centres with strong environmental information systems (e.g. National Polytechnic School — EPN; San Francisco University of Quito — USFQ; Ikiam Regional Amazonian University; Latin American Faculty of Social Sciences — FLACSO Ecuador; Technical University of Loja — UTPL).

POLICY RECOMMENDATION 4: *Public experimentation: designing policies that learn through practice*

Socio-environmental challenges require policies capable of adapting to complex and changing contexts. In many cases, solutions cannot be fully defined from the outset but must be developed progressively based on institutional learning. In this context, it is essential to promote public experimentation approaches that allow solutions to be tested on a small scale before being scaled up. Instruments such as pilot programs, policy laboratories, or participatory evaluations can facilitate institutional learning processes, allowing policies to be adjusted based on the experience accumulated in the territories.

Key actors:

- Innovative local governments (e.g. Municipality of Cotacachi; Municipality of Quito)
- Civil society organisations specialised in public policy innovation and social experimentation (e.g. Esquel Foundation; Ñeque Foundation ; FARO — Policy and Social Innovation Group)
- International development organisations with field presence (e.g. Italian-Ecuadorian Fund for Sustainable Development — FIEDS; PLAN International)
- Applied research institutions (e.g. National Polytechnic School — EPN; Andean University Simón Bolívar — UASB, Latin American Faculty of Social Sciences — FLACSO Ecuador)

POLICY RECOMMENDATION 5: *Just transitions: designing policies that recognise the duality between sustainability and development needs*

The initiatives analysed show that many territories in the Global South operate in a dual condition. On the one hand, they face growing pressures to move toward ecological transitions related to climate change, ecosystem conservation, and new global sustainability agendas. On the other hand, conditions of material insufficiency persist, linked to employment, income, access to services, and economic opportunities. This duality creates a structural tension between environmental sustainability goals and the need to improve the living conditions of the population. When environmental policies are designed by replicating models developed in other contexts, these tensions can intensify. It is therefore necessary to promote just transitions that explicitly integrate environmental objectives and social well-being, strengthening territorial economies, generating sustainable livelihoods, and avoiding shifting the costs of ecological transformations to vulnerable communities.

Key actors:

- Indigenous and territorial organisations with representative capacity and rooted legitimacy in communities affected by the unequal social and ecological costs of transition and development (e.g. the Union of Peasant and Indigenous Organizations of Cotacachi - UNORCAC, Kallari Association, the Confederation of Indigenous Nationalities of Ecuador - CONAIE, the Confederation of Indigenous Nationalities of the Ecuadorian Amazon - CONFENIAE, and the Ceibo Alliance).
- Environmental justice and territorial defence organisations that challenge extractivist models (e.g. Ecological Action, Amazon Frontiers).
- Solidarity economy and community-based financial organisations that can help sustain livelihoods without subordinating territorial life to extractive growth imperatives (e.g. Maquita Foundation).
- Urban grassroots collectives that respond to climate and livelihood pressures through self-organised practices of sufficiency (e.g. Participatory Urban Agriculture Project of Quito - AGRUPAR; Zero Waste Ecuador Alliance).
- Local governments in affected territories, engage with demands for just transitions, territorial livelihoods, and socially grounded ecological policy (e.g. Municipality of Cotacachi, Municipality of Tena, Municipality of Quito).

In summary, the Ecuadorian case shows that moving towards sustainability requires policies capable of engaging with initiatives that are already emerging from the territories, recognising their knowledge, organisational capacities, and ways of relating to nature. Taken together, these recommendations suggest the need to rethink sustainability policies from a territorial, relational, and adaptive perspective.

5.1.1 Key policy areas in the Ecuadorian wellbeing trajectories

Across the wellbeing trajectories analysed in the Ecuadorian case, the key policy areas are those that shape the conditions under which community-based initiatives can sustain territorially grounded, sufficiency-oriented, and ecologically embedded forms of wellbeing. Rather than offering an exhaustive policy mapping, this section highlights the main domains in which public policy can better recognise, enable, and support these trajectories.

- **Territorial and land governance policy:** recognition and protection of community relations to territory, including land-related conditions that shape the viability of collective projects, local autonomy, and culturally grounded forms of wellbeing.
- **Agri-food and community-based production policy:** support for small-scale production, value-added processing, productive diversification, and locally rooted forms of economic activity linked to agriculture, cacao, and other community-based livelihoods.

- **Water and basic services policy:** strengthening water infrastructure, maintenance, access to drinking water, and other essential services that directly condition community wellbeing, environmental management, and the continuity of local initiatives.
- **Infrastructure and territorial connectivity policy:** improvement of roads, signage, mobility, and other enabling infrastructures that affect access to markets, circulation between communities, and the practical viability of local economic and social initiatives.
- **Community economic diversification and tourism policy:** support for income diversification, microenterprises, community-based tourism, and other locally embedded strategies that strengthen economic resilience without detaching livelihoods from territorial and cultural foundations.
- **Education, training, and capacity-building policy:** expansion of educational opportunities, technical training, project formulation capacities, leadership development, and other learning processes identified as necessary for strengthening community agency and long-term sustainability.
- **Institutional support, coordination, and enabling regulation:** better articulation between community organisations and public institutions through stronger policy support, inter-institutional collaboration, institutional recognition, and regulatory conditions that do not undermine the viability of community-based initiatives.

References

- Acosta, A. (2017). Living Well: Ideas for reinventing the future. *Third World Quarterly*, 38(12), 2600–2616. <https://doi.org/10.1080/01436597.2017.1375379>
- Altmann, P. (2016). Buen Vivir como propuesta política integral: Dimensiones del Sumak Kawsay. *Mundos Plurales - Revista Latinoamericana de Políticas y Acción Pública*, 3(1), 55–74. <https://doi.org/10.17141/mundosplurales.1.2016.2318>
- Angresius, L., Büchs, M., Greselin, A., & O’Neill, D. W. (2025). *Towards post-growth policymaking: Barriers and enablers for wellbeing economy and Doughnut economics government initiatives*. arXiv. <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2501.17600>
- Bermúdez-Restrepo, C., & Vaca-López, A. (2026). Critical Contributions of Buen Vivir (Sumak Kawsay) as a Latin American Alternative to Global Sustainability. *Sustainability*, 18(2), 1–17. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su18020622>
- Bhatia, R., Pihlajamaa, M., & Hirvilammi, T. (2024). Rethinking Transformative Innovation Policy in the Context of Post-Growth. Paper presented at Eu-SPRI Annual Conference 2024, Enschede, Netherlands.
- Bodirsky, B. L., Chen, D. M. C., Weindl, I., Soergel, B., Beier, F., Molina Bacca, E. J., ... & Lotze-Campen, H. (2022). Integrating degrowth and efficiency perspectives enables an emission-neutral food system by 2100. *Nature Food*, 3(5), 341–348.
- Brand, U., Görg, C., & Wissen, M. (2020). Overcoming neoliberal globalization: Social-ecological transformation from a Polanyian perspective and beyond. *Globalizations*, 17(1), 161–176. <https://doi.org/10.1080/14747731.2019.1644708>
- Buenting de Almeida Rego, C. (2021). Understanding Cape Town’s food system through grassroots innovations and social-technical transitions theory Stellenbosch. Stellenbosch University. <https://scholar.sun.ac.za/items/29bfba1a-04aa-479f-b8a1-c2f2abfc9576&ved>
- Büchs, M., & Koch, M. (2017). *Postgrowth and Wellbeing*. Springer International Publishing. <https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-59903-8>
- Büchs, M., Rilla, N., Angresius, L., Bedoya, L., Bhatia, R., Campos, M., Cuestas Caza, J., Nieminen, M., Toledo, L., & Wiman, H. (2023). Framework for the case studies. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13682846>
- Cachipuendo, C., Sandoval, J., & Requelme, N. (2026). La cosmovisión andina y la crianza sabia del agua en territorios irrigados: Caso acequia Tabacundo - Ecuador. *Agua y Territorio: Water and Landscape*, (29), 213–230. <https://doi.org/10.17561/at.29.8352>

- Carranza-Barona, C., & Villalba-Eguiluz, U. (2026). Socioecological transitions that transcend hegemony: From co-optation to resistance regarding Buen Vivir in Ecuador. *Environmental Science & Policy*, 176, 104320. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envsci.2026.104320>
- Chakori, S., Grigg, N. J., Biely, K., Hinton, J. B., Plumecocq, G., Richards, R., & Robra, B. (2026). From innovation to exnovation: insights from post-growth food enterprises in Australia. *Ecological Economics*, 239, 108785.
- Chassagne, N. (2019). Sustaining the ‘Good Life’: Buen Vivir as an alternative to sustainable development. *Community Development Journal*, 54(3), 482–500. <https://doi.org/10.1093/cdj/bsx062>
- Churuchumbi, G. (2014). Usos cotidianos del término sumak kawsay en el territorio kayambi [Tesis de Maestría, Universidad Andina Simón Bolívar]. <http://repositorio.uasb.edu.ec/handle/10644/4055>
- Coral-Guerrero, C. A., García-Quero, F., & Guardiola, J. (2021). What is Sumak Kawsay? A Qualitative Study in the Ecuadorian Amazon. *Latin American Perspectives*, 48(3), 35–50. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0094582X211004913>
- Cuestas-Caza, J. (2021). El Sumak Kawsay: Entre el (post)desarrollismo occidental y la filosofía andina [Tesis Doctoral, Universidad Politécnica de Valencia]. <https://riunet.upv.es/handle/10251/162882>
- Cuestas-Caza, J., Toledo, L., & Rodríguez, F. (2024). Transcultural bioeconomy governance in a plurinational state: Sumak Kawsay and bio-based production in two Kichwa territories of Ecuador. *Forest Policy and Economics*, 163, 103227. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.forpol.2024.103227>
- Cramer, C., Di John, J., & Sender, J. (2022). Classification and Roundabout Production in High-value Agriculture: A Fresh Approach to Industrialization. *Development and Change*, 53(3), 495-524.
- D’Alisa, G., & Kallis, G. (2020). Degrowth and the State. *Ecological Economics*, 169, 106486. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecolecon.2019.106486>
- DEAL. (2024). *Cities & Regions | DEAL*. <https://doughnuteconomics.org/themes/cities-regions>
- Escobar, A. (2005). El “postdesarrollo” como concepto y práctica social. En D. Mato (Ed.), *Políticas de economía, ambiente y sociedad en tiempos de globalización* (pp. 17–31). Facultad de Ciencias Económicas y Sociales, Universidad Central de Venezuela.
- Escobar, A. (2015). Degrowth, postdevelopment, and transitions: A preliminary conversation. *Sustainability Science*, 10(3), 451–462. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11625-015-0297-5>
- Escobar, A. (2018). *Designs for the Pluriverse: Radical Interdependence, Autonomy, and the Making of Worlds*. Duke University Press. <https://doi.org/10.1215/9780822371816>
- Escobar Urbina, G., Bedoya, L., & Cuestas-Caza, J. (2025). Pathways to Sustainable Wellbeing in Ecuador. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15645968>

Faccer, K., Nahman, A., & Audouin, M. (2014). Interpreting the green economy: Emerging discourses and their considerations for the Global South. *Development Southern Africa*, 31(5), 642–657. <https://doi.org/10.1080/0376835X.2014.933700>

Feola, G. (2025). Postgrowth food systems: critique, visions, pathways. *Degrowth Journal*, 3, 1-23.

Garcia-Arias, J., & Cuestas-Caza, J. (2024). Pluriversal Autonomies Beyond Development: Towards an Intercultural, Decolonial and Ecological Buen Vivir as an Alternative to the 2030 Agenda in Abya Yala/Latin America. *Latin American Perspectives*, 51(4), 122–140. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0094582X241292327>

Gerber, J.-F., & Raina, R. S. (2018). Post-Growth in the Global South? Some Reflections from India and Bhutan. *Ecological Economics*, 150, 353–358. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecolecon.2018.02.020>

Grcheva, L., & Vianello, M. (2025). Doughnut Economics in Local Governments: An Overview of Emerging Practice. *Journal of City Climate Policy and Economy*, 4(2), 258–299. <https://doi.org/10.3138/jccpe-2025-0002>

Guandinango, Y. (2013). Sumak Kawsay – buen vivir: Comprensión teórica y práctica vivencial comunitaria, aportes para el ranti ranti de conocimientos [Tesis de Maestría]. Facultad Latinoamericana de Ciencias Sociales

Hayden, A. (2025). Buzzword or breakthrough beyond growth? The mainstreaming of the Wellbeing Economy. *Ecological Economics*, 227, 108375. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecolecon.2024.108375>

Herselman, M. and Mahwai, N. (2025). Pathways of sustainable Well-being in South Africa: WP3 – ToBe South Africa Team Report | 2024 Fieldwork Findings.

Hickel, J., & Kallis, G. (2020). Is Green Growth Possible? *New Political Economy*, 25(4), 469–486. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13563467.2019.1598964>

Hossain, M. (2016). Grassroots innovation: A systematic review of two decades of research. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 137, 973-981. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2016.07.140>

Hough-Stewart, L., & Janoo, A. (2024). Policy Design for a Wellbeing Economy—Lessons from Four City Pilots. *Journal of City Climate Policy and Economy*, 2(2), 204–220. <https://doi.org/10.3138/jccpe-2023-0008>

Inuca, B. (2017). Genealogía de alli kawsay / sumak kawsay (vida buena / vida hermosa) de las organizaciones kichwas del Ecuador desde mediados del siglo XX. *Latin American and Caribbean Ethnic Studies*, 12(2), 155–176. <https://doi.org/10.1080/17442222.2017.1325101>

Jacobs, M. (2016). Green Growth. In R. Falkner (Ed.), *The Handbook of Global Climate and Environment Policy* (2nd ed.) (pp. 132–142). Wiley-Blackwell.

- Johnson, G., Whittington, R., Scholes, K., Angwin, D., & Regner, P. (2017). Exploring strategy: Text and cases (11th ed.)
- Kallis, G., Hickel, J., O'Neill, D. W., Jackson, T., Victor, P. A., Raworth, K., Schor, J. B., Steinberger, J. K., & Ürge-Vorsatz, D. (2025). Post-growth: The science of wellbeing within planetary boundaries. *The Lancet Planetary Health*, 9(1), e62–e78. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S2542-5196\(24\)00310-3](https://doi.org/10.1016/S2542-5196(24)00310-3)
- Koch, M. (2020). The state in the transformation to a sustainable postgrowth economy. *Environmental Politics*, 29(1), 115–133. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09644016.2019.1684738>
- Kothari, A., Salleh, A., Escobar, A., DeMaria, F., & Acosta, A. (2019). Pluriverso: Un diccionario del posdesarrollo. Icaria Editorial. <https://dialnet.unirioja.es/servlet/libro?codigo=742627>
- Kushitor, S. B., Drimie, S., Davids, R., Delpont, C., Hawkes, C., Mabhaudhi, T.,...Pereira, L. M. (2022). The complex challenge of governing food systems: The case of South African food policy. *Food security*, 14(4), 883-896. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1007/s12571-022-01258-z>
- Lang, M. (2022). Buen vivir as a territorial practice. Building a more just and sustainable life through interculturality. *Sustainability Science*, 17(4), 1287–1299. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11625-022-01130-1>
- Lewis, W.A. (1954), Economic Development with Unlimited Supplies of Labour. *The Manchester School*, 22: 139-191. <https://doi-org.libproxy.helsinki.fi/10.1111/j.1467-9957.1954.tb00021.x>
- Malo Larrea, A., Ambrosi de la Cadena, M., Collado Ruano, J., & Gallardo Fierro, L. (2024). Transcending the nature-society dichotomy: A dialogue between the Sumak Kawsay and the epistemology of complexity. *Ecological Economics*, 216, 108044. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecolecon.2023.108044>
- Manolchev, C., Watson, D., Colombo, L. A., Elf, P., & Vandeventer, J. S. (2024). A means to an end? The role of technology in growth and post-growth futures of agrifood work in a European context. In *The Handbook for the Future of Work* (pp. 237-250). Routledge.
- Martinez-Alier, J. (2014). The environmentalism of the poor. *Geoforum*, 54, 239–241. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.geoforum.2013.04.019>
- Mason, N., & Büchs, M. (2023). Barriers to adopting wellbeing-economy narratives: Comparing the Wellbeing Economy Alliance and Wellbeing Economy Governments. *Sustainability: Science, Practice and Policy*, 19(1), 2222624. <https://doi.org/10.1080/15487733.2023.2222624>
- McGreevy, S. R., Rupperecht, C. D., Niles, D., Wiek, A., Carolan, M., Kallis, G., ... & Tachikawa, M. (2022). Sustainable agrifood systems for a post-growth world. *Nature sustainability*, 5(12), 1011-1017. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41893-022-00933-5>
- Messham, E., & Sheard, S. (2020). Taking the long view: The development of the Well-being of Future Generations (Wales) Act. *Health Research Policy and Systems*, 18(1), 33. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12961-020-0534-y>

O'Neill, D. W., Fanning, A. L., Lamb, W. F., & Steinberger, J. K. (2018). A good life for all within planetary boundaries. *Nature Sustainability*, 1(2), 88–95. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41893-018-0021-4>

Pixová, M., Spanier, J., Guerrero Lara, L., Smessaert, J., Sandwell, K., Strenchock, L., Lehner, I., Feist, J., Reichelt, L. & Plank, C., (2025) “Building solidarities and alliances between degrowth and food sovereignty movements”, *Journal of Political Ecology* 32(1): 5841. doi: <https://doi.org/10.2458/jpe.5841>

Polanyi, K. (1944). *The Great Transformation: The Political and Economic Origins of Our Time*. New York, Farrar and Rinehart.

Quick, J., & Spartz, J. T. (2018). On the Pursuit of Good Living in Highland Ecuador: Critical Indigenous Discourses of Sumak Kawsay. *Latin American Research Review*, 53(4), 757–769. <https://doi.org/10.25222/larr.132>

Raworth, K. (2017). *Doughnut Economics: Seven Ways to Think Like a 21st-Century Economist*. Chelsea Green Publishing.

Raina, R. S., & Kachroo, R. (2024). Post-growth agrifood systems: Towards an emancipatory politics. *Review of International Studies*, 50(5), 898–909. doi:10.1017/S0260210524000408

Rockström, J., Steffen, W., Noone, K., Persson, Å., Chapin, F. S., Lambin, E. F., Lenton, T. M., Scheffer, M., Folke, C., Schellnhuber, H. J., Nykvist, B., de Wit, C. A., Hughes, T., van der Leeuw, S., Rodhe, H., Sörlin, S., Snyder, P. K., Costanza, R., Svedin, U., ... Foley, J. A. (2009). A safe operating space for humanity. *Nature*, 461(7263), 472–475. <https://doi.org/10.1038/461472a>

Roman-Alcalá, A. (2017). Looking to food sovereignty movements for post- growth theory. *Ephmera*.

Smith, T. S. J., Baranowski, M., & Schmid, B. (2021). Intentional degrowth and its unintended consequences: Uneven journeys towards post-growth transformations. *Ecological Economics*, 190, 107215. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecolecon.2021.107215>

Steffen, W., Richardson, K., Rockström, J., Cornell, S. E., Fetzer, I., Bennett, E. M., Biggs, R., Carpenter, S. R., de Vries, W., de Wit, C. A., Folke, C., Gerten, D., Heinke, J., Mace, G. M., Persson, L. M., Ramanathan, V., Meyers, B., & Sörlin, S. (2015). Planetary boundaries: Guiding human development on a changing planet. *Science*, 347(6223), 1259855. <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.1259855>

Storm, S. (2015), Structural Change. *Development and Change*, 46: 666-699. <https://doi-org.libproxy.helsinki.fi/10.1111/dech.12169>

te Wierik, S., DeClerck, F., Beusen, A. et al. (2025). Identifying the safe operating space for food systems. *Nature Food* 6, 1153–1163. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s43016-025-01252-6>

Yüksel, İ. (2012). Developing a multi-criteria decision making model for PESTEL analysis. *International Journal of Business and Management*, 7(24), 52–66

van den Bergh, J., & Kallis, G. (2012). Growth, A-Growth or Degrowth to Stay within Planetary Boundaries? *Journal of Economic Issues*, 46(4), 909–919. <https://doi.org/10.2753/jei0021-3624460404>

van Huyssteen, T., Nonhebel, S., & Thiam, D. (2023). The Sustainability of Agri-Food Trade in South Africa. Available at SSRN 4524899. <https://doi.org/http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4524899>

Vargas-Chaves, I. (2025). Repensando el desarrollo desde el sur: El Sumak Kawsay como paradigma constitucional y de la cosmovisión indígena. *Trans/Form/Ação*, 48, e025138. <https://doi.org/10.1590/0101-3173.2025.v48.n4.e025138>

Welsh Government. (n.d.). *The Well-being of Future Generations*. Retrieved November 13, 2024, from <https://www.gov.wales/well-being-of-future-generations-wales>

Wright, E. O. (2019). *How to be an anticapitalist in the twenty-first century*. Verso Books.

Ziai, A. (Ed.). (2007). *Exploring post-development: Theory and practice, problems and perspectives* (First issued in paperback). Routledge.

Ziai, A. (2017). Post-development 25 years after *The Development Dictionary*. *Third World Quarterly*, 38(12), 2547–2558. <https://doi.org/10.1080/01436597.2017.1383853>

Appendix 1: European agrifood policy labs

The first workshop, “Grass-Root Transformation of Food system: Food security and Food sovereignty”, focused on a critical reflection from a Global-Local and Global South (G-S) perspective. We explored the role of community-driven agrifood initiatives for sustainable well-being in Ecuador and South Africa. The workshop deployed a participatory approach to critically examine what political, economic, social, legal and technological drivers and barriers for similar food systems transformation lie within the EU. The concrete aim of the lab was to identify innovative approaches, including social and technological innovations and related policy frameworks, that foster a profound transformation of food systems.

The second workshop, “Grass-Root Transformation of Food system: Europe’s Food Sovereignty Future, 2050”, deepened the primary findings of the first lab. We explored systemic transformation towards a sustainable wellbeing economy and what role food system transformation plays in it. The workshop deployed co-creation methods and back-casting to identify and find actionable strategies and policy pathways for structural transformation. By creating a future vision based on the results from the first lab, we identified ways to overcome institutional and economic barriers to food sovereignty to strengthen the role of local communities and farmers as key agents of change.

In total, 75 different policy options were identified across different levels and policy spheres. These included social and mindset change, regulations and policies, networks and social movements, local policies, STI policy and business and industry sector changes. From those policy options, participants identified seven most important drivers that were translated as policy recommendations.

Appendix 2: South African policy labs

In 2025, two Policy Lab Workshops were held in South Africa. The first event took place in Pretoria on 6 May, and the second in Cape Town on 8 May, focusing on sustainability and policy tensions in the South African agrifood sector. These workshops focused on government officials and practitioners involved in the agrifood sector, green innovations, and the economy, as well as sustainable transitions in South Africa, aiming to develop context-sensitive policy options for sustainable futures.

These workshops also explored the sovereignty approach and aligned technological and social innovations to support transitions beyond growth towards sustainable and just societies. During these Policy Lab Workshops, we explored the policy instruments (strategies, regulations, incentives, and funding instruments), actors (farmers, communities, and minority groups), and levels (national, regional, and local) required to support sustainability transformation. The workshops in Cape Town and Pretoria focused on transforming the current system by addressing policy and regulations to prioritise agrifood systems, engaging more youth in agriculture, and increasing access to various markets for small-scale farmers.

Timeline of Fieldwork and Participatory Activities in South Africa

Appendix 3: Territorial research and fieldwork in Ecuador

The fieldwork carried out in Ecuador as part of the ToBe project was structured as a progressive process of territorial research aimed at understanding how the notions of well-being, sustainability, and sufficiency are articulated in indigenous community contexts. Between 2023 and 2026, multiple immersions were carried out in the province of Imbabura, particularly in the canton of Cotacachi, as well as in the organizational experience of Kallari, located in the canton of Tena (province of Napo), in the Ecuadorian Amazon. These activities combined exploratory field trips, participatory workshops, and spaces for exchange with local actors, with the aim of identifying organizational practices, productive initiatives, and ways of relating to nature that dialogue with the horizon of Sumak Kawsay. This process allowed us to build a situated understanding of territorial dynamics, incorporating both the experience of community organizations and the perspective of institutional actors linked to local development.

A total of 47 in-depth interviews, three participatory workshops, and various follow-up activities with community organizations and local institutions were conducted, allowing for the triangulation of evidence from fieldwork, collective reflection, and dialogue with different actors. As part of this process, a Policy Lab was also developed in the city of Quito, bringing together seven participants from NGOs, foundations, universities, and environmental activism to discuss the implications of these findings for

public policy design. This set of activities constitutes the empirical basis for the analysis presented in this paper and underpins both the theoretical perspective adopted and the policy recommendations developed in the following sections.

Timeline of Fieldwork and Participatory Activities of the Ecuador Team in the ToBe Project